

THE EFFECT OF PARTICIPATIVE LEADERSHIP ON INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOUR: A MEDIATING ROLE OF SELF-EFFICACY

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Abstract

In today's fast changing world, technology and innovation are considered integral part of the organizations' success. Leading those organizations need leadership that promote the innovation and creativity keeping in mind the well being of most important resource of the organization i.e., employees. According to the Job demand and resource model, low levels of leadership affect employees' work demand while high levels of leadership will increase the work resources of employees. Job resources have been shown to be strongly and positively associated with teachers' well-being and job satisfaction which in return increase their self efficacy. Higher levels of self efficacy of employees result in positive outcomes. They tend to solve problems on their own by finding innovative solutions to deal with challenges. The purpose of the study is to examine the effect of participative leadership on innovative work behaviour with the mediating affect of self efficacy. A total of 323 respondents were chosen from privates schools of Peshawar, KPK region. The results of analysis showed that participative leadership has a positive effect on self efficacy with in return positively affect innovative work behaviour of the employees. Also the direct effect of participative leadership on innovative work behaviour was significant.

INTRODUCTION

The Educational landscape in the present competitive world shows that the effectiveness of service delivery is really vital for educational institutions (Petruzzellis and Romanazzi, 2010). To achieve this objective, every educational organization requires a strong leader, as leadership is the core of any institution that can foster high-quality service delivery (Chebonye et al., 2021). Educational institutions serve as crucial settings where future generations are shaped, placing significant responsibility on school leaders for their organizations. Leaders in educational settings face challenges similar to those in other types of

organizations, as they must consistently work to uphold the institution's goals (Northouse, 2010).

In order to ensure the success of educational institutions in this unpredictable environment, it is essential to adopt a leadership style that facilitates the implementation of necessary teaching procedures (Torlak and Kuzey, 2019). It was found that the determinants which can affect teachers' well being while trying to explore the factors affecting teacher's turn over (McInerney, Korpershoek, et al, 2018). Besides a leadership style of school principal, the factor affecting school performances is the teacher's job satisfaction. Northouse (2010) suggested that "teachers' job satisfaction may play a role in

influencing their morale, motivation, and overall willingness to maximize their teaching capabilities.” Leaders of schools, including heads, principals, and managers, are expected to have the capability to influence their staff, stakeholders and parents to be clear that their education system can achieve their intended goals by guaranteeing that teachers fulfill their duties effectively and that students excel academically as expected. Turnover and retention of teachers have been issues that have been significantly worsening in an upward trajectory over the last few years. It is not only an urgent crisis that needs to be resolved; this scenario has triggered an obstacle for schools in retaining teachers. In previous research, teachers who took part mentioned the negative aspects of their jobs which had caused them to be disgruntled with their jobs. Among all factors that have been severely discussed in literature, frequent appearance of two most crucial factors were noted by various research including least participation of teachers in decision-making and low participative leadership at academic institution (Turnbull, 2004). According to a study conducted by Wambane (2015) participative leadership led to better school process. He along with some other scholars went on to conclude that participative leadership enhances organizational and team effectiveness. Sinani (2016) also found that the participative leadership style positively affects the job satisfaction at significance level of 0.01. The research established that where head teachers were participative and were intolerant to different opinions from other teachers, the group worked together as a unit and were encouraged to outdo their past target, resulting in job satisfaction of the teachers (Wachira, Gitumu, and Mbugua, 2017). Most studies on teacher job satisfaction produced findings that school elements such as the conditions of work, teacher-student relationships and school management played a huge role in the entire school community.

The effect of participative leadership on employees is highlighted in research (Bass, 1985; Yukl, 1999). Participatory leadership, characterized by shared decision-making and involvement of employees in organizational processes, has been recognized as a vital leadership style that promotes creativity and innovation among employees (De Jong & Den Hartog, 2007). The advantage of PL is that leaders

do not force employees to accept their decision instead they ask for their opinions and suggestions and take final decision based on those recommendations (Somech & Wenderow, 2006). According to Chen and Tjosvold (2006) decisions that are taken jointly with constructive controversy can be used to listen to the views of others and understand their opinions to solve any problem. So, we can say that participative leaders play an important role in creating organizational learning opportunities to promote creativity and innovation. Understanding how participative leadership effect the commitment of the employees to change along with IWB is crucial in order to understand how leadership fosters change and IWB among employees. If leaders have participative style based on the clarity of knowledge and information, then employees will know that they need to take part in decision making process (Ogbeide & Harrington, 2011). It will promote the motivation and IWB to think about creative ideas as they will feel empowerment and involvement of their leader (Yan, 2011).

The idea that whatever a teacher does is important for students is called teachers’ efficacy which is one of the most powerful predictors of how a teacher effect students. If teachers believe that the school will only be successful due to the intelligence of students, their home environment and may be other factors then chances are that they will not make efforts for students learning. If teachers believe in their efforts and its effectiveness then he/she will make efforts continuously to face the challenges to persevere till the time each and every child is successful and become hardworking student. (Bandura, 1997). Teachers who are efficient will feel satisfied by evaluating their efforts and results of training even without primary education. They will try to improve their teaching skills by using new methods and strategies to get new perspective from their co workers, newspapers, books, training and workshops. The relationship between leadership style of the principal and efficacy of the teachers is mediated by the experiences that teachers experience on job especially job satisfaction (Nir and Kranot 2006). Staggs (2002) suggests that the perception of teachers about the leadership behaviour of their principal effects the teachers’ effectiveness in schools and not just individual teacher effectiveness. Still the

perception of majority of teachers about principal's leadership style will affect overall efficiency of teachers.

Self efficacy, as per social cognitive theory, means a judgment of an individual regarding his/her abilities to perform a job at a specific level (Bandura, 1997). Individuals who have this belief that they can perform given task successfully will put a lot of efforts and will probably get the desired outcomes as they will face the obstacles, and develop the fighting mechanism to manage any setbacks (Bandura, 1986 & 1997). In educational sector, the self efficacy of teacher means "teacher's belief in his or her own abilities to manage and implement actions that are required to successfully achieve a specific teaching task in a specific context" (Woolfolk & Hoy, 1998).

Employees having positive relationship with their leaders try to showcase IWB because of their confidence that their creative actions will help them in gaining performance (Nijenhuis, 2015). The findings of the study showed that self-efficacy positively affects IWB. Feldman (2008) also suggests that, self-efficacy is the belief in one's abilities. People who have high self-efficacy are more patient in doing task to achieve objectives (Feldman, 2008).

According to Gaynor, cited by Prayudhayanti (2014), IWB means any action that will be taken in order to develop and accept creative idea that can be used in the implementation of the task. The leader originates a purpose then plan and organizes the moves to control all resources of the organization in order to get desired outcome efficiently and effectively (Martono, 2013).

Problem statement

Principals of schools, who are leaders, have the responsibility for managing all the talent that exists to get the school goals. Husaini (2008) suggested that the principal (leader) plays a crucial role in leading the school and utilize the resources effectively and efficiently and to be able to implement the vision of school. The ability of the principal to manage each component of the school influences the success or failure in educational system at school (Mulyasa 2012). Lecturers' leadership style will influence in guiding and influencing the academic ability of pupils' job satisfaction and final research (Banjarnahor, 2014).

An institution of formal education is expected to become a center of excellence in all aspects of Human Resource Development (HRD). To accept and support this concept, the key responsibility lies with the principal of school (Sudarmin & Darwin, 2012). Gilbert Austin concluded that the main difference between high-achieving schools with under achieving schools is due to the influence of the principal (Darwin, 2012).

Participatory Leadership makes a kind of leadership that involves employees in taking decision and consultation, by gathering employees' idea and suggestions into consideration before making final decision, also enabling them in taking decision by their leaders to improve the balance between the organization and employees' objectives (Leane, 2013). The opinion suggests that, the principal of school which has participatory style would be able to help teachers' grow their job satisfaction, because the teacher decide school objective, how to achieve the goals, and what needs to do for reaching those goals.

A judgment of one's own abilities to achieve desired goals related to students involvement and learning, even if students are de-motivated or difficult is known as teacher self efficacy. High self-efficacious teachers are always ready to new ideas and teaching techniques; their actions will display high level of task planning and managing, are eager to deal with mistakes of the students, and are more persistent in challenging situations (Tschannen-Moran, Hoy, & Hoy, 1998). As a conclusion, teacher self-efficacy is a theoretical construct that is designed by teachers' own characteristics like gender and teaching experience including classroom performance level. The characteristics of school and principal are highly related to teachers' SE (Fackler & Malmberg, 2016).

The adoption of novelty needs the development of IWB, a process that will help the employee to search for new innovative ideas, promote them to other so shared advantage can be obtained (Carmeli, A., 2006; Lambriex-Schmitz, 2020; Messmann, G., 2011). While the creation of innovative behavior is an infrequent aspect found in employees, the cultivation of creative ideas within the organization does not even lead to the development of the IWB of the members of the school organization. For this process, teachers' thoughts and beliefs are very important mediating determinant that potentially

facilitate or hinder the growth of IWB in teachers (Horng, J.-S., 2005; Mueller, J., 2008).

Furthermore, studies have demonstrated the effect of perceived self-efficacy of teachers on their every single activity throughout their professional life (Cansoy, R., 2018). It refers to how capable teachers feel about their ability to accomplish the school mission well, as well as effectively managing the classroom by fixing the needs and characteristics of each pupil and influencing them to participate while building their characters and personality.

Research has proved that teacher's self efficacy is an important factor that affects IWB. (Horng, J., 2005). At the same time, SE is connected with the passion to come up with creative ideas in their workplace (Ozer, E.A, 2015; Warren, J.M., 2013), while it directs burnout and signals educator exhaustion (Xanthopoulou, D., 2007). Utilizing the JDR belief, that identifies the dimensions of BT, exhaustion and disengagement, it showed that it happens due to the pressure to complete the task within limited period of time (Noefer, K., 2009), as well as integral consideration on the issues that stand in education system (Kimonen, E., 2005), are potential element of IWB development in the way that task demands (Messmann, G., 2011).

On the other hand, the school surroundings, depicting possessions, plays an main duty, and can affect the IWB, in addition to approving occupied environments for the faculty member [Mohammad, R.F, 2008]. In this situation, professional freedom [Nakata, Y., 2011] acts as a starting point for the emergent IWB.

Purpose of research

The research aims to understand the effect of participative leadership on the innovative work behaviour of the faculty that belongs to the HEC recognized private schools of Peshawar, Pakistan. The research will also examine how participative leader affect the innovative work behaviour of the faculty (teachers) with a mediating role of self-efficacy.

Research objectives

1. To examine the effect of participative leadership (PL) on Innovative work behaviour (IWB) in private schools of Peshawar, KPK.

2. To examine the mediating effect of self-efficacy (SE) amongst participative leadership and Innovative work behaviour.

LITREATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Leadership

Leadership has turn into a fast-spreading field of interest for everyone around the world. Initially it was considered a part of widespread field of research based on the study from a classical and military prospect (Yukl, 2013). Later the other two aspects like sociological and intellectual one were also included. Various studies are focusing on the recognition of the practices that can lead to prosperous leadership (Crevani, Lindgren and Packendorff, 2010, p.77) because leadership is visualized as something that can resolve many disputes in any institutions around the world (Palestini, 2009, p.1). The leadership-as-practice approach acknowledges the importance of the actions of leadership such as common exercise and achievements (Crevani and Endrissat, 2016, p.31).

Defining the concept of leadership represents a significantly somewhat recent academic efforts, it remnants and mystery" (Fairholm and Fairholm, 2009, p.5). The fact is that there is no globally agreed description of the leadership theory" (Gosling, et al., 2012, p.xiv)

Participative leadership

The concept of participative leadership was first represented by Barnard in 1938. According to the concept, the members have the time, autonomy and belief that they can generate ideas which will help them to attain their goals. The two main actions that represent participative style of leadership are: one is the input in which employees get involved in the supervisory decision making and the other one is engaging authority where assistants shared their viewpoint with their leader. The three theories like the autonomous leadership belief by Lewin (1943), leadership systems theory by Likert (1967) and Maslow theory (1943) are also considered to be related to the participated leadership theory. According to the Maslow theory (1943), individuals are the ones who are stimulated by need for self-actualization can be stimulated through leadership

style as these individuals will try their best to achieve maximum in their lives to become content.

In business administration, people show affection and confidence in the competence of groups and their subordinates' decisions making where as leaders try to regulate the actions in order to get maximum benefits. Leaders gain workers' confidence and assurance to the task which will result in advanced responsibilities and performances (Huang et al., 2010).

Participative leadership focuses on the environment where employees are given the authority to be involved in the decision making process and suggest their opinions. This, in return, will increase their efficacy while doing their jobs. Leaders can gain the trust of their employees if they involve them in the decision making process (George et al., 2016).

Participative leadership antecedents are vital in guiding for the advancement of leadership research. In recent times, there are two major antecedents of participative leadership. One is individual -level and the other one is the organizational-level. A lot of the work in the field of research is done on individual experiences and leader-member differences which are considered as individual-level antecedent. These factors show that leaders act in display more participative behaviour. On the other hand, organizational controls try to make leaders put greater emphasis on the importance of participation of employees' indecision making process it is proven that the size of the organization and its culture effect the participative leadership behaviour of a leader.

Innovative Work Behaviour

IWB means identifying the issues, developing new and realistic plans relevant to product/services and work designs, as well as possessing the enough behaviour to demonstrate and complete activity these plans focusing to improve individually or in business. In accordance with present styles in recruiting, most of organizations check candidates' intelligent and creative skills to make sure these recruited members will use their innovative behaviour to solve problems (Delgadová, et al., 2017). Different institutions give importance to changing leadership styles as leaders are crucial role effecting IWB and self efficacy of the employees (Strom, et al., 2014).

According to the Janssen (2000), IWB is basically actions or behaviors that promote creation of new ideas and their implementation within the organizations. He also noticed that "these excess function behaviors concern discretionary member conduct that surpass recommended role intentions, and are not straightforwardly or specifically acknowledged by the precise reward system" (p. 289). Research literature shows that schools are the primary source of education and capabilities which mainly depend upon the leadership style as it will provide direction and help teachers to be creative and innovative in their teaching career (Husin, & Khalid, 2018). Although research provide plenty of information about education and its sources but a little is known about the key factors that affect the behaviors of the employees like IWB (Burns & DiPaola, 2013; Srivastava & Dhar, 2019).

There are many determinants that reinforce the creative work of the workers, but leadership was seen as ultimate conspicuous specific determinant that advances the production of such performance between workers (Huang, Wu, Lu & Lin, 2016), so, leadership has frequently existed submitted all at once of the key factor that can promote creativity and innovation at work. The reason is that leaders have the ability to provoke the Innovative behaviour at work with the right attitude and strategies (Wu & Lin, 2018). Established various literature learning, individual determinants that influence innovative work behavior are abilities (OECD, 2010), inspiration (S.-C.Chen, 2010, T. Yidong, 2016; A. Bandura, 1997), self-efficacy (A. Bandura, 1997, M. Momeni, 2014) and administrative commitment [I. Ajzen, 1991].

The current measures of IWB, shows different aspects of innovation process. According to Scott and Bruce, it is a process of multiple stages. Similarly Kantar (1988) mentioned three steps for IWB. They are idea generation, coalition building and the implementation. When we think of innovative individual, he/she will start the process with the identification of a problem and coming up with the ideas to solve them in a creative way. Then such innovative individual will try to find someone who will be willing to sponsor the idea by coalition building and will make efforts to get support for it.

In the end, the same individual will try to come up with ways in which the idea can be implemented. Participative leaders do not feel any insecurity or hesitation while sharing authority with their workers. The result of such behaviors show positive outcome as the employees automatically felt satisfied and do good performance (Miao et al, 2014). In simple words, employees' will try to copy their leader and show positive results like IWB. Based on these results, the current research suggests that participative leaders influence employees to show Innovative work behaviour (Bandura, 1977).

H1: Participative leadership positively affects employee's innovative work behavior.

Social cognitive theory

Self-efficacy

The concept of self efficacy can be defined as the individual's belief that he/she can deal with the difficult jobs and it is considered as the crucial determinant for affecting Human behaviour(Bandura, 1997). In case of teachers, self efficacy means the beliefs related to their competencies and capabilities to perform their job (teaching) even though having difficult students in class. It is believed that this influences the behaviour

Among the theories related to the individual learning behaviors, is the social cognitive theory. According to this the learning behaviors in social context happens due to the interactions between environment, people and their behavior (Bandura, 1986). Individuals and groups get knowledge and insights from other individuals' behaviors and actions. Learner's social reinforcement (internal and external) is dependent on the interactions between other groups and individuals (de Guerrero and Villamil, 1994). Other than that the personal experiences also play important role in the intellectual development and learning behaviors. According to Bandura, learners' past experiences influence their expectations and this will transform their motivation, involvement and actions, their expectations related to the outcome of tasks (Yunus et al., 2021).

of the teachers and other outcomes (Woolfolk Hoy, & Hoy, 1998).

It is believed that teachers with higher level of self efficacy will work really hard, try to participate in learning activities even if they are informal, have less anxiety and are more persistent (Bandura, 1997; Lohman, 2006). That's why; the result of this belief will be high level performance (Ross, 1998). A lot of studies have shown positive effect of teachers' self efficacy with many other outcomes which were

related to the teachers' performance. One outcome was student achievement (Ross, 1992) while the other includes motivation (Eccles, 1989). Some others examined the relationship between teachers' well being and job satisfaction (Steca, 2003).

The main idea of Social cognitive theory is that individuals perform in a specific way because of the judgments' of other people about their abilities to manage and perform tasks and achieve specific performances (Bandura, 1986). He named this self efficacy and suggested that along with the skills required to perform a job, the opinions of other people will affect actions and behaviors of individual, Bandura (1997). Skills are necessary to perform certain tasks but self efficacy belief will explain the reasons if the tasks are not accomplished. At the same time, self efficacy belief clarifies how capabilities can be improved due to job accomplishment (Campion, 2005).

According to Bandura (1997), there are three dimensions of self efficacy namely magnitude, strength and generality. The first dimension is the magnitude which represents the degree of difficulty and an individual feels while doing it. It can be explained by an example that when an individual is given different tasks based on the level of difficulty, he/she may choose easy, moderate or difficult task based on the individual's self efficacy belief, perceived ability and behavioral demand to perform that task. The level and demand for the task shows different challenges to perform successfully Rodgers et al. (2008).

The second dimension is the strength which shows the amount of strength/stability of the individual when he/she faces difficult situation. Bandura (1997) believed that self efficacy affects the course of actions which will give outcomes according to the expectations and hope of the individuals. The third dimension is the generality when an individual has the confidence that he/she can achieve or complete the task regardless of the situation. It shows the belief an individual has about himself to avoid the failures in different situations.

Previous researches provide evidences that organization will be effective if they have creative employees (Amabile, 1996). Recently, many researchers and scholars are trying to search conditions that make employees more creative.

Employees' creativity and innovation is encouraged by the participative leadership (Krause, Gebert & Kearney, 2007; Somech, 2006). Literature also show that it is important for the employees to participate in solving organizational problems through creativity and innovation but the problem lies with the most of the organizations where leaders do not perform participatory role as they are scared to lose their position and power (White 1981). In contrast, the leaders who show participatory behaviour by encouraging employees to bring improvement of the ongoing activities make employees feel empowered and motivated to come up with creative solutions for the problems (Abraham & Hayward, 1985).

Self efficacy beliefs are due to four main factors namely mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, social persuasion and physiological/emotional states Bandura (1977). Individual will have higher self efficacy due to successful task accomplishment and the failure can negatively affect this belief. In order to develop self efficacy, individuals with lack of self confidence, observe their fellow worker to learn ways to perform any task. This will build their self efficacy and they will be able to achieve their objectives (Wise & Trunnell, 2001). Mastery experiences help people to develop the self efficacy (Pajares, 2002) as compared to the vicarious experiences.

Verbal persuasion (social persuasion) means when individuals receive appreciation or approval from others verbally. Words play a powerful role in developing higher self efficacy but the negative persuasion can destroy the belief of the individual as they are most powerful as compared to positive persuasion (Pajares, 2002). Similarly, anxiety, stress and fear can destroy individual's self efficacy as they believe they cannot perform the task as per expectations or they feel they do not have the capabilities to do the job properly (Bandura and Adams, 1977). This shows how emotional and physiological states affect individuals' self efficacy.

Teachers never work in isolated environment (Hoy & Tarter, 2007). The personal and school level performances of the teachers are greatly affected by the extent in which the teachers will collaborate with others (Firestone & Pennell, 1993; Lally & Scaefe, 1995). That is why it's important for the principal to create an environment for the teachers to collaborate with other staff. Participative leadership is found to

be highly effective only if the collaboration is genuine and authentic (Hoy, 2000). So we can say that:

H2: Participative leadership positively affects employee's self-efficacy.

Prior researches have shown the role of self efficacy and the innovative work behavior in organization. According to the Momeni et al., (2014) employees who have higher level of self efficacy, show innovative work behaviour. Similarly, Bandura (1997) suggested that individual who belief they can perform any job, will show innovative work behaviour in the organizations. He suggested that employees with high level of self efficacy can perform well at work and will show innovative work behaviour. So, our 3rd and 4th Hypothesis are:

H3: Self-efficacy positively affects employee's innovative work behavior.

H4: Self efficacy mediates the effect of participative leadership on employee's innovative work behavior.

Job demand and Resources (JD-R) model

The Job demand and resource model (JD-R) shows the outcomes and performance along with the job commitments in various fields (Schaufeli & Taris, 2014).

Job demand includes all those social, physical and emotional aspects that are necessary to maintain cognitive and physical skills. They also come with the costs of these aspects examples include the unpleasant work environment, emotionally straining interactions with others and even high level of work pressure. As per Meijman and Mulder, (1998), these demands may not be negative but can turn into one if individuals do not have the skills and abilities to do the task.

Job resources are those parts of a job that will focus on achieving desired goals by minimizing the demands and costs. It will promote individual growth and development in different areas. According to the JD-R model, high job demands cost employees health by giving them emotional strains. On the other hand, the resources of the employees will affect their involvement and engagement known as process of motivation (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014).

JD-R and leadership

Prior studies have recorded that enabling leadership is powerfully linked with the health of educators like teachers,, lecturers' ability to take part in charge and solving challenges on their own (Suleman et al., 202). JD-R model explains that in the absence of leadership employees' job demands will increase, while in the presence of leadership employees' task resources will increase, which will be affecting organizational outcomes (Schaufeli, 2015). Participative leaders are more in consideration of shortening the capacity distance accompanying lecturers, giving more independence, and helping to increase their task delight by freeing job stress and exhaustion (Liu at al. 2021).

JD-R and teachers' innovative work behaviour

According to previous researches which demonstrate that organizational attributes like task capital and task demands are antecedents in education system which increase of job exhaustion (Lorente 2008).

Bakker, Hakanen, Demerouti and Xanthopoulou (2007) research using task demands- resources (JD-R) model showed that novelty too helps the system in keeping up with changing environment that take place with the learners. JD-R model is regarded as framework and it has been used in many fields, including academics. One study by Dicke and others, (2018) also backed definite partnership of task resources and educators' engagement. Others believe that JD-R model also leads to IWB of the employees (Van Hootegeem, 2014).

JD-R and employees' self-efficacy

Teachers having access to the job resources can experience self efficacy. These resources include autonomy, positive feedback from supervisor, development and growth opportunities, learning and experiencing new skills (Choochom, 2016). Job resources effect the job satisfaction of the teachers and their well being which in return effect on the students' academic performance and their achievements in education (Barbieri et al., 2019).

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model depicts how work-related practices or policies negatively affect health issues, foremost tiredness and exhaustion (Hakanen and Bakker, 2017). So school teachers' job demands and possessions prove

teachers' work-accompanying welfare (Hakanen et al., 2006).

The JD-R model differentiates between two processes. One is job demand which can lead to stress and anxiety in employees and can affect their health negatively. The other one is job resources which can be considered as a motivational resource. It will affect the teachers in a positive manner by increasing their well being and job satisfaction (Bakker & Demerouti, 2006).

Past researches show that teachers with low self efficacy will affect the discipline issues of students along with low level of motivation (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2016). Research also shows that too many job demands will negatively affect teacher's self efficacy where as teaching experiences positively affect their efficacy and can be considered as the job resource for teachers.

Conservation of resources (COR) theory

Hobfoll (1989) presented a theory called the Conservation of Resources belief (COR). It is a good establishment for understanding stress and its association with the resources like demand and supply. Job exhaustion is a work-connected stress that arises under overdone assigned work and pressure and leads to strength and emotional tiredness in addition to diminished performance. According to the COR, exhaustion working happens as a result of seen or real deficit of energy under task demands. For professors, extra workload is tiring. In the lack of support, the work will lead to task tiredness. The information containing plentiful studies on task exhaustion of teachers and tiredness, has found expected ultimate reasons and effect of burnout (Taris and others. 2005).

COR theory suggests that individuals who have a lot of resources are less scared of losing them as compared to the ones having lesser resources (Hobfoll et al., 2018). Some individual traits may be viewed as individual private possessions which means at what extend they generally aid stress fighting" (Hobfoll, 1989; p. 517). COR also suggest that the resources at start can help to reduce the chances of resource misfortune (Hobfoll and others., 2018). Self-efficacy in directing negative despairs can be respected as an individual's self managing system that helps teachers to not be fearful of resource loss.

According to the COR theory, a mindful leader is also a job resource because it can reduce the teacher turnover. According to the JD-R model, the supplying of task resources can help reducing the negative effect of task demands, fear of further loss of money (Schaufeli, 2017).

Self-efficacy also provides reasons to motivation by doing the challenges, the effort they give, and their diligence regardless of obstacles. Finally, in accordance with the Conservation of Resources (COR) hypothesis (Hobfoll, 2001), self-efficacious staff members grant permission, see or build more resources. Indeed, the COR theory envisions that those the one retain more resources are further more gifted of ability gain (Hobfoll, 2001).

Resource-based view theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) is a model in which employees show cooperation and reduce the differences in order to get best possible outcome within organization (Cooner & Prahalad, 1996). It suggests that business must have unique or different resources that can help them attain competitive advantage (Peteraf, 1993).

As far as unique resource idea is concerned, the RBV theory suggests that the resource should fit in the framework of VRIO. This was developed by Barney (1991) in his work 'Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage'. He suggested that the resource should be rare and imperfectly imitable which means no one can easily copy your resource easily. Other than that it should be valuable and non-substitutable which means it should be unique and its substitute should not be made easily Barney (1991).

A research conducted in Malaysia by Alyani, Osman & Bachock (2014) was about the understanding of the determinants which affect parents and their decisions while enrolling kids in any private institute. It showed that parents will choose a private institution based on teachers' quality level, the academic results of the institution and number of facilities provided by the institution. Nevertheless, mainly, private organizations provide these, and accordingly they are not in themselves changing determinants that intrigue guardians to choose anyone school over another. (Alyani, Osman & Bachock 2014).

In general, university and schools allow beating their rivals if they can apply the RBV idea. Therefore, organizations including academics have an enduring back-and-forth competition on account of their devote effort to something recognizing and managing their talent potential to improve their institutions. Strategic leaders have the ability to discover the paths to access the new job resources and motivate employees to achieve the goals by sharing the vision. It will help employees to communicate their knowledge and understanding which will take them

towards the innovative work behaviour and accepting the change in a system (Boal and Schultz, 2007). Individual firms can be successful if they utilize their human resource which can be rare and important resource (Hitt and Ireland, 2002). It is the responsibility of the leader to increase the human capital as it will create value for the organization and will give them competitive advantage. Eventually, it will improve the performance of the businesses with the effective leadership and innovative thinking of the employees (Hitt and Ireland (2002).

Research Framework

Before the final study, a pilot study was done from employees of private schools of Peshawar, KPK to reveal accurate results and omit errors wherever required. The study aimed to develop and test the measures for participative leadership, Innovative work behaviour and self-efficacy. The data was collected randomly from teachers and their responses were examined to confirm the accuracy of the instrument. The questionnaire had brief introduction to help questionnaires understand the purpose of the study.

METHADODOLOGY

It's a quantitative and cross-sectional research as it was performed in a given period of time to answer the research questions using empirical data. The research is performed to test the existing theories rather than forming a new one. The teaching staff (permanent/visiting) of HEC recognized private schools were chosen for the research.

The population included 12 Private sector schools included Bloomfield Hall Peshawar, IIUI school Peshawar, Root millennium school Peshawar, Racines School Peshawar, Beaconhouse School Peshawar, Peshawar Model school, Frontier Model School, Allied school, The Edex school, Park Turk Maarif International School, The City School and Lahore Grammer school. While gathering data, a simple random sampling method was used to gather data from the faulty of HEC recognized private schools of district Peshawar, KPK. To collect data from teachers, questionnaires were distributed both online and through hard copies.

Majority of the data was collected by visiting faculty personally and the rest of the data was collected online using Google forms. The online link was shared with the faculty of private school teachers only. The sample size was decided by taking into account the population size. According to PSRA, the total numbers of private schools in Peshawar district that are registered with HEC are 1689. The sample

size was calculated using the formula $n = \frac{N}{1 + n(e)^2}$. The sample size of 323 respondents was determined using the sample size formula (Yamane, 1967) i.e. $n = \frac{N}{1 + n(e)^2}$ with 95% confidence level and $e = 0.05$

Pilot Study

The pages of the questionnaires were numbered in order to track respondents. The pilot study was done at Bloomfield Hall School in Peshawar, KPK. Bloomfield hall is an educational system of Pakistan which was established in the year 1984. The purpose of the institution is to facilitate students by giving them British style of education. Data was collected from total 96 teachers who participated in the pilot study.

Participative leadership

To measure the Participative leadership variable, 6 items indicating perception of the employees regarding their leader, was measured to examine whether leader encourage their employees to take part in decision making process or not (measurement by Den Hartog, 1997).

Innovative work behaviour

For Innovative work behavior, a measurement including four dimensions i.e., idea exploration, idea generation, idea champion, and idea implementation by De Jong and Den Hartog (2010) and Messmann and Mulder (2012) was used. Two items used were about idea exploration. Three items were used for idea generation, two items for idea championing and two for idea implementation were used.

Self efficacy

Self-efficacy used a measurement scale based on the three dimensions namely strength, magnitude and generality. Among the 8 item, 2 items were used for strength dimension, 3 were used for magnitude and three for generality (Bandura, 1997). The responses were collected using 5-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= agree and 5= strongly agree)

Reliability of research Instrument

Cronbach’s Alpha reliability test was used to examine the internal consistency of the Research instruments, Alpha was developed by Lee Cronbach’s in 1951 (Cronbach’s L, 1951). In addition, reliability estimates show the amount of measurement error in a test. Cronbach’s alpha is considered excellent if reliability is greater than 0.90. Reliability between 0.8-0.9 is considered really good. If reliability is between 0.7 - 0.8, it is considered good. Reliability score between 0.6-0.7 is moderately reliable. However, if the reliability is equal to 0.6 then it’s questionable and below 0.6 is considered as poor (Hair et al., 2003)

* $\alpha \geq 0.7$

Table below shows that all the subsets are internally consistent measures. The total alpha co-efficient is 0.93. On the subscale Participative leadership with respect to the rest of the factors is comparatively low i.e., 0.85 but has a positive correlation. The subscale Innovative work behaviour has the highest alpha coefficient i.e., 0.92. Generally, the results for all subscales show significant reliability i.e., 0.93.

Serial no.	Research instrument	No. of items	Cronbach’s Alpha α
1.	Participative Leadership	6	0.85
2.	Innovative work behaviour	9	0.92
3.	Self-efficacy	8	0.89
	Total	23	0.93

ANALYSIS

It was done in SPSS. Results show Frequency distribution, descriptive statistics, regression, Barron and Kenny’s (1986) method, and PROCESS v4.2 by Andrew F. Hayes. Sobel test was also used, because of its statistical power, to check the significance of the mediation effect of variable, self efficacy.

Regression Analysis

Linear Regression is a method which is used to measure or predict the relationship between two or more variables. It tells us the effect of independent variable(s) of the dependent variable. If there is one independent and one dependent variable in the model then simple linear regression method is used but if there are two or

more independent variables in a model then multiple regression method is used.

Description of Variables

Participative leadership	Independent variable	X
Innovative work behaviour	Dependent variable	Y
Self- Efficacy	Mediator Variable	M

Demographic Profile

Variables included in demographic are gender, age, marital status, qualification, nature of employment and work experience.

The descriptive statistics show that females outnumbered male. The frequency percentage shows that 86.1 percent respondents were female and 13.9 percent were male respondents. Also, majority of the respondents i.e., 140 are between the age group of 31-40 years that is 43.3 percent. 41.8 percent belong to age group between 20-30. 12.4 percent respondents are between 41-50 and 2.5 percent are 50 and above. 63.8 percent of the

respondents were married and 36.2 percent were single.

Majority of the respondents hold Masters/M.Ed degree (58.5 percent). 21.4 percent have done Bachelors/B.Ed, 18.0 percent have done MS/Mphil and 2.2 percent hold PhD degree and 93.8 percent employees were regular/permanent and 6.2 percent were visiting faculty. Lastly, 66.9 percent respondents had less than 10 years of work experience. 27.6 percent respondents had between 11-20 years of work experience and 5.6 had work experience of more than 20 years.

The following table shows the details:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender				
female	278	86.1	86.1	86.1
Male	45	13.9	13.9	100.0
Marital status				
Married	206	63.8	63.8	63.8
Single	117	36.2	6.2	100.0
Qualification				
Bachelors/B.Ed	69	21.4	21.4	21.4
Masters/M.Ed	189	58.5	58.5	79.9
MS/MPhil	58	18.0	18.0	97.8
PhD	7	2.2	2.2	100.0
Nature of employment				
Regular/permanent	303	93.8	93.8	93.8
Visiting faculty	20	6.2	6.2	100.0
Work experience				
11-20 years	89	27.6	27.6	27.6
Less than 10 years	216	66.9	66.9	94.4
more than 20 years	18	5.6	5.6	100.0

Barron and Kenny’s Approach

Barron and Kenny’s approach is used whenever there is a mediator variable in the model.

Mediator (M) is a variable that acts as an intervening variable. The mediation process help us in understanding the role and effect of

mediating variable between the independent and dependent variables. It can show partial or complete mediation in a process. According to Baron and Kenny’s (1986) four step process is required in order to for establishing mediation. First, in step 1, it is required to show that independent variable (X) is correlated with the

dependent variable (Y). Step 2 should show that the variable (X) is correlated with the mediator (M). STEP 3 should show that the mediator (M) affects the variable (Y), while variable (X) is used as control variable. Step 4 is required to establish that M-variable completely mediates the X-Y relationship.

(Adapted from Baron and Kenny, 1986)

Model and Interpretation:

Step 1

According to the first step of the Baron and Kenny’s approach, the significance of the relationship between independent and dependent variable is being tested. It is mandatory for the association between the dependent variable (Y) and independent variable (X) to be significant.

The Co efficient (Beta) value for PL is .383 which shows a positive relationship between PL and IWB. This means that 1 unit increase in participative leadership will increase .383 units of Innovative work behaviour. The t value is 9.359 and significance value is less than 0.05 that is 0.001. Based on the statistics and significance

value, we accept first hypothesis H1 that is Participative positively affects IWB.

Step 2 The Second step of Baron and Kenny’s (1986) approach is to conduct mediation analysis. The independent variable (X) should be correlated to the mediator variable (M) showing significant relationship.

The coefficient value (Beta) is .370. This means that 1 unit increase in participative leadership will increase .370 units of Self efficacy. The t value is 9.364 and significance value is less than 0.05 that is 0.001. Based on the statistics and significance value, we accept our second hypothesis H2 i.e. participative leadership positively affects employee’s self-efficacy.

Co-efficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.683	.157		17.113	<.001
	PL	.383	.041	.463	9.359	<.001

a. Dependent variable: IWB

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.773	.151		18.339	<.001
PL	.370	.039	.463	9.364	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: SE

Step 3 According to the Baron and Kenny’s approach, the third step should show the mediator (M) affects the dependent variable (Y).The coefficient value (Beta) is .808. This means that 1 unit increase in self efficacy will increase .808 units of Innovative work behaviour. The t value is 22.306 and significance value is less than 0.05 that is 0.001.

Based on the statistics and significance value, we accept our third hypothesis H3 i.e. Self-efficacy positively affects employee’s innovative work behavior and significance value is less than 0.05 that is 0.001. Based on the statistics and significance value, we accept our third hypothesis H3 i.e. Self-efficacy positively affects employee’s innovative work behavior.

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.760	.152		4.992	<.001
average of SE	.808	.036	.780	22.306	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: IWB

STEP 4 The last step of Baron and Kenny’s approach is to establish that Mediating variable (M) completely mediates the X-Y relationship. APROCESS v4.2 by Andrew F. Hayes is used to test whether the model supports partial or complete mediation. The mediator variable is introduced and the result should make the previous association between the independent variable (X) i.e

participative leadership and dependent variable i.e. innovative work behaviour (Y) insignificant while making the association significant between the mediator (M) and the dependent variable (Y). This will ensure complete mediation. The partial mediation happens when the association among the independent and the dependent variable remains the significant but the beta value of the independent variable decreases after the mediator is introduced (barren and Kenny, 1986).

OUTCOME VARIABLE

The table shows that the value of R square is .6211 which means that 62.1%change in criterion variable (dependent variable) is due to the change in

predictors (independent variable and mediator). The p values are less than 0.05 which shows significant relationship.

IWB						
Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.7881	.6211	.1083	262.2410	2.0000	320.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	.6142	.1561	3.9362	.0001	.3072	.9213
PL	.1073	.0321	3.3407	.0009	.0441	.1705
SE	.7459	.0402	18.5322	.0000	.6667	.8250

Model : 4

Y: IWB (Innovative work behaviour)

X: PL (Participative leadership)

M: SE (Self efficacy)

Sample

Size:323

Total effect of X on Y					
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.3829	.0409	9.3592	.0000	.3024	.4634
Direct effect of X on Y					
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.1073	.0321	3.3407	.0009	.0441	.1705
Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:					
	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
SE	.2757	.0566	.1731	.3936	
Total effect = direct effect + indirect effect c = c' + ab					

According to the table 4.12, the total effect of independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) directly, and the effect of independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) through mediating variable (M) is .3829 and p value is .0000 which is less than 0.05 which means it's significant. Direct effect of independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) is .1073 and p value is .0009 which is less than 0.05 which means it's significant. The indirect effect of independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) through the mediator (M) is .2757 shows

that mediation exists between the X and Y variables. It shows that if the mediator (M) changes then it will affect the X and Y variable by .2757. The LLCI (lower limit confidence level) is .1731 and ULCI (upper limit confidence level) is .3936 both of them are positive values without any zero between them which means that the effect of mediator (M) i.e., Self Efficacy significantly mediates between independent variable (X) i.e., Participative leadership and dependent variable (Y) i.e., Innovative work behaviour.

Barron and Kenny's model with values

According to the figure, the beta value of the predictor has reduced from .383 to .1073 and the relationship between the independent and dependent variable was significant after the mediating factor was introduced. The findings

suggest partial mediation in this case. Hence we accept the fourth hypothesis H4 i.e. Self efficacy mediates the effect of participative leadership on employee’s innovative work behavior.

Sobel Test

Sobel test	Statistics	p-value
	8.455	0

In order to check the significance of the mediation effect, we use Sobel test. This tool was proposed by the Sobel in 1982. This test measures the relationship between independent variable and dependent variable and how it is affected by the mediating variable. Table shows the statistical value which is 8.455 and p-value is 0 which is less than 0.05. It shows that this path is significant and that mediation exists.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The aim of the research was to find the effect of participative leadership on the innovative work behaviour with the mediating factor, self efficacy. The study was conducted in the private schools of Peshawar, KPK to find how participative leadership affects self-efficacy of faculty (teachers) which in return affects innovative work behaviour.

According to the Mitzberg, (2010), leaders possess the characteristics that will motivate the employees to work towards collective goals as per vision as it is essential for the success of the organizations. Also, leaders have the ability to affect the behaviors of the employees as the role of a leader is also changing in the recent times. The success of any institution/businesses depend upon the leader and his/her leadership style (Saleem, Tufail, Atta & Asghar, 2015). In order to survive, it is necessary for the organization to identify the type of leadership that will influence the IWB of the employees (Kark, Van Dijk & Vashdi, 2018).

According to Bandura, self efficacy is essential in performing difficult tasks as it affects decisions of individual and achievement (Bandura, 2000). Based on the same theory, it was found that people will have self-control and even self regulations when they want to achieve anything. These mental activities affect the behaviors of the individual. Bandura believed that only having knowledge, skills and

previous achievement are not enough to perform well in future, instead, a person’s belief to complete various duties and tasks will affect their performances quality (Bandura, 1997).

According to the JD-R model, depressed levels of leadership will likely infuriate laborers’ work demands, while extreme levels of guidance will likely improve employees’ work resource and work outcomes (Schaufeli, 2015). Empowering leaders are more in consideration of increasing the capacity for teachers, bestowing autonomy and more independence and spirit to increase their job satisfaction by lowering task stress and tiredness and putting educators/teachers in a better position commotion their tasks (Liu at al., 2021).

COR hypothesis suggests that things accompanying better possessions are less vulnerable to source misfortune and more accomplished of support gain (Hobfoll and others. 2018). In the workplace, self-efficacy in directing negative concerns has existed demonstrated to be a main individual tendency in facilitating negative belongings induced by work-accompanying stress (Caprara and others. 2013).

The results of the current study confirm that participative leadership positively affects the self efficacy of the employees which in return positively affects the innovative work behaviour.

Recommendations:

1. This study is a cross-sectional study and the data was collected and analyzed for a specific period of time only. For future, a longitudinal study may reveal same or contradictory results.
2. The data was collected from the private schools only. The results may vary if data is collected from public schools. Also, data from colleges and universities can also explore new areas for further research.

3. The data is collected from HEC recognized private schools of Peshawar region. The other regions were excluded in the study. Different regions may reveal different results based on many other factors. For example, climate, culture, ethnicity etc.

4. This study uses quantitative approach; future study may include both quantitative and qualitative approach.

5. A mediating factor is self-efficacy which can be replaced by other factors in future to examine the relationship between leadership style and innovative work behaviour.

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